

A PROGRESSIVE FAILURE MODEL FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITES CONTAINING AN OPENING

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Abstract

A progressive failure model is developed for laminated composites containing stress concentrations and subjected to in-plane loading. The key of this approach is to model a damaged lamina using a damaged ply constitutive relation in a simplified manner. The environmental effects including the thermal residual stresses and hygroscopic stresses are taken into consideration. Parametric studies show that load increment only has little effect on the ultimate strength. When the number of elements for the finite element mesh increases to a certain magnitude, the predicted ultimate strength approaches a stable value. The predictions for the ultimate strength, stress-strain behavior and the damage progression agree well with the experimental result.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ultimate strength of laminated composites containing stress concentrations has been able to be predicted very well using semi-analytical methods [1-2]. Recently, more interests have been placed on the progressive failure modeling. The mechanisms for the damage progression and accumulation in laminated composites containing stress concentrations are extremely complicated. They are a combination of matrix cracking, fiber/matrix splitting, fiber breakage and delamination, etc. These failure mechanisms are so complicated that analytical methods are unpractical and, perhaps, unable to model them. In the author's opinion, the

most suitable tool is the finite element methods.

Another key issue involves in the progressive failure modeling of laminated composites is that it contains some three-dimensional effects. For instance, a matrix crack of a ply within a multidirectional laminate creates three-dimensional boundary conditions. However, if this problem is to be solved using a three-dimensional approach, it needs a tremendous amount of calculations. Between the complications and accuracy needed, simplifying assumptions are bridges that need to be built across them.

Earlier investigators, such as [3] and [4], have shown promising results using progressive failure models although they have not taken thermal residual stresses and stresses due to moisture content into account. The present model includes these environmental effects because they could have significant effects on the damage progression and ultimate strength of the laminates. Parametric studies were conducted to show the mesh size effect and the load increment effect. Finally, the predictions for the ultimate strength and the damage accumulation for laminated composites containing a central hole were examined with the experimental results.

2. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 Constitutive Relations

The constitutive relations of an anisotropic undamaged material, in the laminate axes, can be written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{16} \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & Q_{26} \\ Q_{16} & Q_{26} & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x - \epsilon_{xN} \\ \epsilon_y - \epsilon_{yN} \\ \gamma_{xy} - \gamma_{xyN} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}$ are the lamina stresses; $Q_{ij}, i, j = 1, 2, 6$, are the lamina stiffnesses; $\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}$ are the total strains and $\epsilon_{xN}, \epsilon_{yN}$ and γ_{xyN} are the non-mechanical strains or initial strains. The off-axis stiffnesses Q_{ij} can be expressed in terms of on-axis stiffnesses C_{ij} which are given in engineering properties E_{11}, E_{22}, G_{12} and ν_{12} . The relations between Q_{ij} and C_{ij} can be found in any standard textbook. The non-mechanical strains of Eq.(1) are written more explicitly as

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xN} &= \alpha_x \Delta T + \beta_x \Delta H \\ \epsilon_{yN} &= \alpha_y \Delta T + \beta_y \Delta H \\ \gamma_{xyN} &= \alpha_{xy} \Delta T + \beta_{xy} \Delta H \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_x &= V_1 + V_2 \cos 2\theta \\ \alpha_y &= V_1 - V_2 \cos 2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (3a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{xy} &= 2V_2 \sin 2\theta \\ \beta_x &= V_3 + V_4 \cos 2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (3b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_y &= V_3 - V_4 \cos 2\theta \\ \beta_{xy} &= 2V_4 \sin 2\theta \end{aligned}$$

and the invariants, V_1, V_2, V_3 and V_4 are

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) \\ V_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \\ V_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(\beta_1 + \beta_2) \\ V_4 &= \frac{1}{2}(\beta_1 - \beta_2) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where α_1 and α_2 are the thermal expansion coefficients in the 1 and 2 (parallel and transverse to fiber) direction, respectively; β_1 and β_2 are the hygroscopic expansion coefficients in the 1 and 2 directions, respectively. The term ΔT is the temperature

change from the stress-free state to the operating temperature and ΔH is the specific

state to the operating condition.

2.2 Construction of an Element

Eq.(1) can be rewritten in a compact form as

$$\{\sigma\} = [Q]\{\epsilon\} - [Q]\{\epsilon_N\} \quad (5)$$

The Jacobian matrix was applied to correlate the local coordinate system and the global coordinate system. Utilizing the strain-displacement relations of an elastic material, we obtain the element strains in terms of nodal displacements:

$$\{\epsilon\} = [B]\{q\} \quad (6)$$

where $[B]$ is a matrix depending on the geometry of the element and

$$\{q\} = \{u_1 \ v_1 \ u_2 \ v_2 \ u_3 \ v_3 \ u_4 \ v_4\}^T \quad (7)$$

Using the principal of virtual work [5], we obtain the following equation by equating the external virtual work to internal virtual work:

$$\{q^*\}^T \{F\} = \int_V \{\epsilon^*\}^T \{\sigma\} dV \quad (8)$$

i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{Virtual} \\ \text{nodal} \\ \text{displacements} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{Actual} \\ \text{nodal} \\ \text{forces} \\ \text{per volume} \end{array} \right] \\ &= \int_V \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{Virtual} \\ \text{strains} \\ \text{caused} \\ \text{by } \{q^*\} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{Actual} \\ \text{element} \\ \text{stresses} \end{array} \right] dV \end{aligned}$$

Considering the virtual displacements $\{q^*\}$ for the strain-displacement relations of Eq.(6) and substituting $\{\epsilon^*\}^T$ into Eq.(8) results in

$$\{q^*\}^T \{F\} = \int_V \{q^*\}^T [B]^T \{\sigma\} dV \quad (9)$$

Since $\{q^*\}^T$ is arbitrary and not a function of position, Eq.(9) reduces to

$$\{F\} = \int_V [B]^T \{\sigma\} dV \quad (10)$$

Combining Eqs.(5), (6) and (10) we finally obtain the nodal force-displacement relations

$$\{F\} = \int_V [B]^T [Q] [B] \{q\} dV - \int_V [B]^T [Q] \{\epsilon_N\} dV \quad (11)$$

In the case that the thickness of the laminate is constant, Eq.(11) can be simplified to

$$[K] \{q\} = \{F\}/t + \{R_N\} \quad (12)$$

where

$$[K] = \int_A [B]^T [Q] [B] dA \quad (13)$$

$$\{R_N\} = \int_A [B]^T [Q] \{\epsilon_N\} dA$$

where $[K]$ is a 8x8 symmetric matrix and $\{F\}$ as well as $\{R_N\}$ are 8x1 column matrix.

When a laminate is formulated rather than a ply, the ply stiffnesses, $[Q]$ matrix, Eq.(5), are replaced by the laminate stiffnesses, $[A]$ matrix, which can be calculated through the use of laminated plate theory.

3. DAMAGED LAMINA FORMULATION

The effective in-plane constitutive relations of a damaged composite lamina containing matrix cracks and fiber breakage can be written in the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1 &= D_1^{-1} S_{11} \sigma_1 + S_{12} \sigma_2 \\ \epsilon_2 &= S_{12} \sigma_1 + D_2^{-1} S_{22} \sigma_2 \\ \epsilon_6 &= D_6^{-1} S_{66} \sigma_6 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where lamina coordinates and contracted notation have been assumed, D_1 , D_2 and D_6 are the internal state variables representing the damaged state of the lamina. In terms of common engineering terminology, D_1 is the stiffness degradation factor of a lamina along the fiber direction caused by fiber breakage; D_2 and D_6 are the stiffness degradation factors transverse to the fiber direction and shear component, respectively, due to matrix failure. Note that the inverse of these internal state variables, D_i , have been used in Eq.(14) rather than D_i in the author's previous paper [6, 7]. The reason of this slight alteration is simply because D_i of Eq.(14) are the stiffness degradation factors which can be shown as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= D_1 E_{11}^0 \\ E_{22} &= D_2 E_{22}^0 \\ G_{12} &= D_6 G_{12}^0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} are the effective damaged lamina stiffnesses and

E_{11}^0 , E_{22}^0 and G_{12}^0 are the undamaged lamina stiffnesses. In Eqs.(14) and (15), the internal state variables D_1 , D_2 and D_6 are less than unity if damages have occurred in the lamina. As we pointed out in reference [6, 7] these internal state variables are a function of the crack density or crack spacing and are laminate dependent. Unfortunately, those findings complicate the finite element formulation of the damaged element.

In this study, we only want to obtain the first order effect by assuming that D_1 , D_2 and D_6 of a lamina are not dependent on the orientation of the constraint plies. In this regard, these D_i are treated as material properties. When a damage occurs in a lamina of an element, the crack density of the element is calculated as one crack per element length. The internal state variables D_i can be estimated from our earlier work [6, 7]. No sufficient theoretical study has been made for the degradation of D_1 . Therefore, D_1 is evaluated from a parametric study which will be shown later in Section 6. The value of D_1 was found between 0.001 to 0.07 and D_2 and D_6 are approximately 0.2 for the material systems discussed in this paper.

4. FAILURE CRITERIA

In-plane failure can generally be classified into matrix failure and fiber breakage. Each of these failure mechanisms can be caused by a uniaxial stress or combined stresses. From the previous section, we see that the stiffness degradations of a lamina do not depend on how the damages were caused. In other words, a failure mode caused by either a uniaxial load or combined load results in the same stiffness degradation factors. For this reason, we only need to distinguish the failure modes by matrix failure or fiber breakage. Among the existing failure criteria, Tsai-Wu criterion [8] has been extensively studied. Therefore it is adopted in this analysis. One concern about

using the Tsai-Wu criterion is that it does not distinguish failure modes. In an earlier paper [1], a failure condition across the fibers of a longitudinal lamina has been successfully utilized to predict the strength of composite laminates containing stress concentrations. The lamina-based fiber failure condition states that

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X X'} + \sigma_1 \left(\frac{1}{X} - \frac{1}{X'} \right) = e_f \quad (16)$$

where σ_1 is the stress along the fiber direction and X and X' are the respective tensile and compressive strength of a 0° laminate. When $e_f \geq 1$, the laminate has failed. Eq.(16) has been used successfully to predict the strength of laminated composites under tensile and compressive loading, uniaxial or combined loading [2]. In this application, we again assume that fibers have broken when $e_f \geq 1$. The prediction of fiber failure by Eq.(16) maybe somewhat conservative because it does not consider the strengthened effect due to combined stresses, such as the combination of σ_1 and σ_2 stresses. However the magnitudes of σ_2 and σ_6 could be very small just before the ultimate failure because the matrix cracks release the stresses at the crack surfaces. If Tsai-Wu criterion predicts that a damage has occurred but e_f of Eq.(16) is less than unity, then matrix failure has occurred. In terms of strength ratio, Tsai-Wu criterion states that

$$[F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j] R^2 + [F_i \sigma_i] R - 1 = 0 \quad (17)$$

when $R \leq 1$, the failure has occurred. Once a failure has occurred in a lamina in the form of matrix cracking or fiber breakage, the constitutive relations, Eq.(14), are applied for the damaged lamina of the element considered.

5. COMPUTATION PROCEDURES

Two computer programs were written for this study. One program, **FEMESH**, generates the finite element mesh. The users only need to input the dimensions of the plate, the hole radius and the number of divisions desired for the plate. Another program, **PROFAS**, carries out the computations of the modeling, which are explained in the following:

1. Input the element node numbers, nodal coordinates, boundary conditions, material properties, laminate lay-up and thickness ratio, temperature change and

moisture content change from the stress free state.

2. Construct the element stiffness matrix and non-mechanical force vector in global coordinates so that simple addition of each element leads to structural stiffness matrix and non-mechanical force vector. The final form is similar to Eq.(12).

3. Solve the nodal displacements with the prescribed zero displacement boundary conditions and the applied nodal boundary forces.

4. Compute the total strains at the Gaussian points. Using these results we calculate the laminate stresses through the use of effective laminate properties. The ply stresses are then calculated using the current constitutive relations, Eq.(14).

5. Check the damage state using Eqs.(16) and (17) for the fiber breakage and matrix cracking, respectively. Proceed with any of the following conditions:

- 5.1 If no damage was detected. Go to step 3 with the next load increment, $p = p + \Delta p$.

- 5.2 If matrix has failed, substitute the lamina constitutive relations by the damaged lamina constitutive relation, Eq.(14). The element stiffnesses are the average values of the four Gaussian points. Recalculate the structural stiffness matrix, step 2. Then go to step 3 with the next load increment, $p = p + \Delta p$.

- 5.3 If fiber has broken, we calculate the load redistribution due to the damage. This is a major failure, therefore, we iterate the calculation for the stress and strain redistributions at a constant applied load. The iteration procedure is to replace the constitutive relations by Eq.(14) and go to step 2 until no additional fiber failure has occurred. Then set up next load increment and go to step 2.

6. After damages are detected, reflected by the internal state variables D_1 , D_2 and D_6 , they are stored permanently in an array and print out for examination. In the case of fiber dominated laminates, the ultimate failure is assumed to occur if the fibers are broken across the entire width of a ply. In the case of matrix dominated failure, fibers are not parallel to the principal loading direction, ultimate failure is assumed to reach when substantial matrix failure has occurred in all the laminae.

6. PARAMETRIC STUDIES

Several studies were conducted that include the stress distribution around the hole using different mesh design, the effect of load increment and the effect of the number of elements for the finite element mesh. They are discussed in the following.

6.1 Stress Distribution

The finite element analysis gives the stress-strain distribution for the entire plate. In particular, the stress concentrations on the axis perpendicular to the loading direction predicted by this finite element code will be compared to the existing analytical solution in this section. In order to show the convergence of the finite element result, we consider three different meshes for 2a (hole diameter) = 0.762 cm (0.3 in.), W (plate width) = 1 in. and L (half specimen length) = 3.81 cm (1.5 in.). These finite element meshes have the same design but differ in element dimensions and number of elements. The result is plotted in Figure 1 for the AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy [0/90 \pm 45]_s laminate containing a hole with $2a/W = 0.762 \text{ cm}/2.54 \text{ cm}$ (0.3 in./1 in.). MESH 1, 2 and 3 represent finite element meshes which contain 42, 115 and 420 elements, respectively. The material properties are listed in Table 1. Since this is a quasi-isotropic laminate, the effective laminate stress concentration factors are the same as those for isotropic plate. The analytical solution represents the infinite plate solution [9,10] multiplied by the finite width correction factor, Heywood formula [11,12]. Figure 2 shows that this finite element result has excellent agreement with the analytical solution except at a small distance near the straight free edge. This phenomenon agrees with some earlier findings [12].

6.2 Effect of Finite Element Mesh

The computing time varies significantly from one mesh design to another depending on the number of elements. Although a finer mesh predicts the failure progression better than a coarse mesh does, it needs more computing time. The increase in computing time may not worth the increase in accuracy after the number of elements reaches a certain value. Therefore, a parametric study is shown in Figure 2 for the tensile ultimate strength of a AS4/3502 Gr/Ep [0/90 \pm 45]_s laminate containing a hole and $2a/W = 0.3$

in./1 in. Three three finite element meshes that were used in Figure 1 were applied for the analysis. The results for D_1 ranges from

0.001 to 0.1 and D_2 and D_6 ranges from 0.1 to 0.3 reveal that the ultimate strength are nearly the same when the number of elements is greater than or equal to 115 elements. Thus, MESH 2 that contains 115 elements will be used extensively later.

6.3 Effect of D_1 , D_2 and D_6

Figure 2 also illustrates the effect of the internal state variables D_1 , D_2 and D_6 . For $D_1 = 0.01$, D_2 and D_6 varies from 0.1 to 0.3, Figure 2a, the ultimate strength changes 24%. For $D_2 = D_6 = 0.2$, D_1 varies from 0.01 to 0.07, Figure 2b, the ultimate strength changes 28%. These stiffness degradation factors, D_1 , D_2 and D_6 , are the percentage of the stiffness retained in a ply of an element after a micro-damage has occurred. This parametric study shows that the ultimate strength of a laminate is quite sensitive to the value of these stiffness degradation factors. The reason of this result can be explained by the following rational analysis:

If the progressive micro-damages of the laminate, given in Section 6.2, release all the stress concentrations, then the gross strength of the laminate is $0.7 \sigma_o$ where σ_o is the ultimate strength of the unnotched laminate. However, if the micro-damages do not release any stress concentration in the laminate, then the gross strength of the laminate is $0.7 \sigma_o/3 = 0.23 \sigma_o$ (based on the maximum stress failure criterion). Based on the average stress failure criterion, it will be $0.23 \sigma_o < \text{gross strength} < 0.7 \sigma_o$. The experimental σ_o is 689 MPa (100 ksi) and the gross strength of this laminate is 324 MPa (47 ksi). The above analysis fully satisfies the experimental result. Therefore, the degree of stress relaxation can result in a large range of ultimate strength. The variation of the predicted ultimate strength due to the changes in D_1 , D_2 and D_6 (28%) is well within the range of this rational analysis ($0.23 \sigma_o$ to $0.7 \sigma_o$).

6.4 Effect of Load Increment

Theoretically, the smaller the load increment is applied, the better this model

predicts the damage accumulation in a specimen. Our criterion is that the load increment should be small enough to capture

the damage progression but large enough to avoid a tremendous amount of unnecessary computing time. The applied nodal forces can be computed by the following equation to obtain the applied laminate stresses:

$$\Delta s = \frac{N \times \Delta p}{W} \quad (18)$$

where N is the total number of nodes along a surface that forces are applied, Δp is the nodal force increment, W is the width of the plate that Δp are acting and Δs is the stress increment of the laminate. The result of Figure 1 shows that the stress distribution predicted by using MESH 2 closely agrees with MESH 3. In addition Figure 2 shows that the ultimate strength predicted using MESH 2 closely agree with those predicted using finer meshes. Thus, MESH 2 is utilized to study the load increment effect. Figure 3 illustrates the predicted ultimate strength of the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate by applying $\Delta s = 13.8, 20.7$ and 34.5 MPa (2, 3 and 5 ksi). The result indicates that the ultimate strength is affected only slightly by the magnitude of the load increment.

However a larger load increment, e.g. $\Delta s > 20.7$ MPa (3 ksi), results in less accurate prediction. The reason is that at one particular stress level the laminate may be just before the ultimate failure, at the next stress level the laminate has been a few MPa beyond the ultimate failure. Figure 3 also shows that the ultimate strength is influenced significantly by the values of the stiffness degradation factors D_1, D_2 and D_6 . The prediction using $D_1 = 0.07$ and $D_2 = D_6 = 0.20$ is 331 MPa (48 ksi) which agrees best with the experimental data, 326 MPa (47.3 ksi).

7. COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENT

The above parametric studies demonstrate the sensitivity of the stiffness degradation factors D_1, D_2 and D_6 upon the ultimate strength of the laminates. However, as we pointed out in Section 3 that simplifying approach has been taken to study this problem. The procedure is to set $D_2 = D_6 = 0.20$ for all material systems and varying D_1 from 0.0 to about 0.10 as a parametric study. After D_1 is evaluated from

a baseline laminate, $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ is used here, it is assumed that D_1 remains the same for all laminates with the same material system. The predictions for the stress-strain relation, the tensile ultimate notched strength and the damage accumulation

at different load levels were examined with experimental results and discussed in the following.

7.1 Stress-Strain Relation

The stress-strain relations of an AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate, 3.81 cm (1.5 in.) wide, containing a 1.55 cm (0.61 in.) diameter hole are predicted along the axis normal to the loading direction. The results are compared to the experimental data, Figure 4, measured by three strain gages located at: (1) $x = 0.0, y = 0.945$ cm (0.372 in.); (2) $x = 0.0, y = 1.285$ (0.506 in.) and (3) $x = 0.0, y = 1.755$ cm (0.691 in.). The predicted initial moduli are the same with or without taking the residual stresses into account. At higher stress level, the stress-strain curves would be affected if the residual stresses were considered. In most cases the residual stresses add damages to a laminate in addition to those caused by the mechanical loading; that additional damages cause extra reduction in the stiffnesses of the laminate.

When the applied stress approaches the ultimate failure load, fiber failure was predicted at a small region near the hole. This is why the predictions at the locations of gage 1 and gage 2 do not continue to the ultimate failure. Although the strain gages 1 and 2 for this particular specimen did not fail prematurely, we did observe fiber failure initiates from the hole boundary and propagates before the ultimate failure in some other specimens with the same lay-up.

7.2 Ultimate strength

The stiffness degradation factors for the AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy material system have been determined using the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate as $D_1 = 0.07$ and $D_2 = D_6 = 0.20$. These values are now used for all the other lay-ups of the same material system. The predicted ultimate strength of the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminates containing a hole with different size are compared to the experimental data in Table 2. When the finite element mesh generator, FEMESH, is utilized, nine radial divisions and seven divisions on the right

hand side of the center square area were maintained the same for all the 2a and W combinations. In the case of a constant laminate width, a mesh with smaller hole radius has more radial rings than a larger hole does. The stress increment for each additional step of the analysis given in Table 2 is $\Delta s = 13.8$ MPa (2 ksi). The predicted tensile notched strength generally

agree well with the data. However, the deviation of the comparison is larger when the hole size is smaller. For instance, the maximum error is 14% for the case when the hole diameter is 0.254 cm (0.1 in.). The predictions without residual stresses are all lower than those with residual stresses taken into consideration. In addition, the specimens were all prepared and tested in a laboratory without exposure to significant amount of moisture. Thus the stresses created by the moisture content is relatively low and did not taken into consideration.

Predictions were also made for the ultimate strength of T300/1034-C graphite/epoxy laminates and compared to the results of Chang and Cheng [4] model in Table 3. Note that the shear strength in reference [4] was evaluated using a $[0/90]_S$ laminate whereas the present model utilizes unidirectional laminate shear strength. The incremental stress for each additional step of analysis is between 6.89 to 13.79 MPa (1 to 2 ksi). The stiffness degradation factors for this material system were evaluated using one specimen following the same procedure as for the previous AS4/3502 material system. In other words, we fix $D_2 = D_6 = 0.20$ and varies D_1 from 0.0 to about 0.1 as a characterization procedure. These factors were obtained as $D_1 = 0.001$ and $D_2 = D_6 = 0.20$. The thermal expansion coefficients and temperature change from the stress free state, ΔT , were not reported and therefore, were guessed from the properties of the T300 fiber and 1034 epoxy as well as their composites with other matrix or fibers. The result in Table 3 shows that the predictions using this model agree closer to the data than the predictions of Chang and Cheng model.

7.3 Damage Accumulation

The damages accumulated in a specimen after being loaded to some stress levels can be detected using x-ray techniques. In order to enhance the radiographic image, diiodomethane was applied around the hole and the free edges. In-plane failure can be

seen clearly from this kind of x-ray radiographs. In this section, the predicted damage accumulations of the present model is examined using the x-ray radiographs.

Figure 5 shows the predicted damages of each ply and the superimposed figure of an AS4/3502 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate containing a hole after the laminate was being loaded to 228 MPa (33 ksi). The predicted damages of

this laminate at 57 ksi are shown in Figure 6. At this load level, many matrix cracks appear in the $+45^\circ$ ply and a small amount of fibers of the 0° ply near the hole boundary has broken. The x-ray radiographs are illustrated in Figure 7a and 7b at 221 MPa and 386 MPa (32 ksi and 56 ksi), respectively. At 32 ksi, a small fiber-matrix splitting occurs in the 0° ply at the opening edge, which is captured by the prediction in Figure 5a. As the load level was increased to 56 ksi, Figure 7b, the fiber-matrix splitting becomes larger. A great deal of matrix cracks were observed in the $+45^\circ$ ply and a smaller number of matrix cracks occur in the -45° ply. The experimental observation basically agrees with the prediction except that no fiber failure was observed in this particular specimen. However, since the load level is very close to the ultimate failure, any deviation from the experimental result should be tolerable.

As an another example, the damage progressions of a AS4/3502 $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate with $2a/W = 0.762$ cm/0.254 cm (0.3 in./1 in.) was analyzed. At 138 MPa (20 ksi), fiber-matrix splittings were detected in the 0° ply. At 207 MPa (30 ksi), a small area of 90° ply and -45° also fail in matrix. At 276 MPa (40 ksi), a small amount of 0° layer near the hole boundary have broken. Matrix cracks have appeared in every ply. When the load was increased to 331 MPa (48 ksi), all the fibers across the net section of the 0° ply have broken. Therefore, this laminate has reached the ultimate failure by definition.

8. SUMMARY, DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

A progressive failure model is developed for laminated composites containing stress concentrations under in-plane loading. This model utilizes ply-by-ply and element-by element analysis. Two failure modes are distinguished: matrix cracking and fiber breakage. Once damages occur in a lamina, the stiffnesses degrade. It is then governed by the damaged lamina

constitutive relations. The effective laminate stiffnesses were recalculated for the elements that contain damaged ply. The redistribution of the stresses can then be computed through the use of the damaged structural stiffness matrix and the appropriate boundary conditions.

In order to reduce the enormous complexity of the problem while maintaining accurate prediction, a few approaches have been taken:

(1) Using stiffness degradation factors D_1 , D_2 and D_6 to model a damaged ply rather than applying a drop-ply technique (total loss of stiffness) as was used by the other investigators. The foundation of this concept has been discussed in the author's earlier papers [6, 7]. The effects of these stiffness degradation factors on the stress relaxation and the ultimate notched strength of the laminates appear to be very significant, Section 6.3.

(2) Conducting parametric studies to show that the predictions approach a stable value once the number of elements for the finite element mesh is larger than a certain value, e.g. 115 elements. This study reveals that a huge number of elements require significant amount of calculations and is unnecessary.

(3) Conducting a parametric study to show the effect of incremental load in each step upon the ultimate notched strength of the laminates. The results suggest that the stress increment for each additional step, Δs , should be between 6.9 to 41.4 MPa (1 to 3 ksi) for most graphite/epoxy laminates. A smaller stress increment may be needed for those laminates that their ultimate strengths are weaker.

The results of this model include the whole field stress-strain relationship, the laminate stiffness degradations and the extent of damages at any stress level. Although this model can be applied to analyze combined in-plane loading, we only discuss the results for orthotropic laminates containing a central hole and subjected to uniaxial tensile loading in this paper. Comparison shows that the predictions correlate closely with the experimental ultimate notched strength and the damaged accumulation after the specimens being loaded to some stress levels. The damage mechanisms of composite laminates subjected to compressive loading is

different than that under tensile loading and, therefore, will be discussed in a subsequent paper.

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Table 3. Comparison of the tensile ultimate strength of T300/1034-C Gr/Ep laminates containing a hole.

Lay-up	Hole Diameter 2a (in)	Plate Width W (in)	Ultimate Strength, σ_N (ksi)		Data
			Present	Chang & Chang [4]	
[0/(\pm 45) ₃ /90 ₃] _S	0.125	0.75	40	33	40.2
[0/(\pm 45) ₃ /90 ₃] _S	0.25	1.50	40	30	37.2
[0/(\pm 45) ₃ /90 ₃] _S	0.125	0.60	38	30	32.8
[0/(\pm 45) ₃ /90 ₃] _S	0.25	1.00	36	26	34.2
[0/\pm 45/90 ₇] _S	0.125	0.75	27	21	27.7
[0/\pm 45/90 ₇] _S	0.25	1.50	27	18	23.0
[0/\pm 45/90 ₇] _S	0.125	0.60	25	18	19.5
[0/\pm 45/90 ₇] _S	0.25	1.00	23	15	23.2
[0/(\pm 45) ₂ /90 ₅] _S	0.125	0.75	33	28	34.3
[0/(\pm 45) ₂ /90 ₅] _S	0.25	1.50	33	25	29.6
[0/(\pm 45) ₂ /90 ₅] _S	0.125	0.60	31	24	25.8
[0/(\pm 45) ₂ /90 ₅] _S	0.25	1.00	29	22	26.9

Figure 1. Normal stress distributions of an AS4/3502 [0/90/±45]_S laminate containing a hole with $2a/W = 0.762 \text{ cm}/2.54 \text{ cm}$ (0.3 in./1 in.).

Figure 2. The effect of the number of elements on the ultimate strength of an AS4/3502 [0/90/±45]_S laminate with $2a/W = 0.762 \text{ cm}/2.54 \text{ cm}$ (0.3 in./1 in.).

Table 1. Material properties of typical graphite/epoxy laminae.**(a) Elastic properties**

Parameter	AS4/3502 GPa (psi)	T300/1034-C GPa (psi)
Longitudinal modulus, E_{11}	143.9 (20.87 x 10 ⁶)	146.9 (21.3 x 10 ⁶)
Transverse modulus, E_{22}	11.9 (1.72 x 10 ⁶)	11.4 (1.65 x 10 ⁶)
Shear modulus, G_{12}	6.7 (0.97 x 10 ⁶)	6.1 (0.89 x 10 ⁶)
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.326	0.30
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient, α_1	-0.899 x 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	0.02 x 10 ⁻⁶ /°C
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient, α_2	23.0 x 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	22.5 x 10 ⁻⁶ /°C
Temperature change, ΔT	-125° C	-140° C
Moisture content change, ΔH	0	0

(b) strength properties

Parameter	AS4/3502 MPa (ksi)	T300/1034-C MPa (ksi)
Longitudinal tensile strength, X	1862 (270)	1731 (251)
Longitudinal compressive strength, X'	1482 (215)	1379 (200)
Transverse tensile strength, Y	52 (7.5)	67 (9.65)
Transverse compressive strength, Y'	207 (30)	268 (38.9)
In-Plane shear strength, S	65 (9.4)	93 (13.5)

Table 2. Comparison of the tensile ultimate strength of AS4/3502 Gr/Ep laminates containing a hole.

Lay-up	Hole Diameter 2a, mm (in)	Plate Width W, mm (in)	$\frac{2a}{W}$	Predicted σ_N MPa (ksi)		Data, σ_N MPa (ksi)
				$\Delta T = 0^\circ \text{C}$	$\Delta T = -125^\circ \text{C}$	
[0/90/±45] _S	2.54 (0.10)	12.7 (0.50)	0.20	372 (54)	386 (56)	436 (63.2)
[0/90/±45] _S	7.62 (0.30)	25.4 (1.00)	0.30	317 (46)	331 (48)	326 (47.3)
[0/90/±45] _S	10.4 (0.41)	34.8 (1.37)	0.29	317 (46)	331 (48)	312 (45.3)
[0/90/±45] _S	15.5 (0.61)	47.5 (1.87)	0.33	317 (46)	331 (48)	272 (39.4)
[0/90 ₂ /0] _S	7.62 (0.30)	25.4 (1.00)	0.30	386 (56)	399 (58)	442 (64.1)
[0/90 ₂ /0] _S	15.5 (0.61)	47.5 (1.87)	0.33	399 (58)	399 (58)	511 (74.1)
[0 ₂ /±45] _{2S}	12.7 (0.50)	25.4 (1.00)	0.50	317 (46)	317 (46)	292 (42.4)
[0 ₂ /±45] _{2S}	5.08 (0.20)	38.1 (1.50)	0.13	552 (80)	552 (80)	562 (81.5)
[0 ₂ /±45] _{2S}	15.5 (0.61)	38.1 (1.50)	0.41	386 (56)	372 (54)	316 (45.9)

Figure 3. The effect of load increment on the ultimate strength of an AS4/3502 $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate with $2a/W = 0.762/2.54$ cm (0.3/1 in.).

Figure 4. The applied stress-local strain relations of an AS4/3502 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2S}$ with $2a/W = 1.55$ cm/3.81 cm (0.61 in./1.5 in.).

Figure 5. Predicted damages of an AS4/3502 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate with $2a/W = 0.762$ cm/3.81 cm (0.3 in./1.5 in.) at 228 MPa (33 ksi).

Figure 6. Predicted damages of an AS4/3502 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2S}$ specimen with $2a/W = 0.762 \text{ cm}/3.81 \text{ cm}$ (0.3 in./1.5 in.) at 393 MPa (57 ksi).

Figure 7. X-ray radiographs of an AS4/3502 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2S}$ specimen with $2a/W = 0.762 \text{ cm}/3.81 \text{ cm}$ (0.3 in./1.5 in.) after loaded to (a) 221 MPa (32 ksi) and (b) 386 MPa (56 ksi).